

Using an Individual Reflective Journal based on the Belbin Team Roles Framework to Manage Group Projects in Large Classes

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Abstract

Group-work, while highly valued, can be challenging to manage in large classes. This paper examines how an individual 'Reflective Journal' (learning log), which requires students to reflect on their experiences and personal learning while undertaking a group project, can be used to enhance group-work and reduce the need for lecturer intervention. Central to the individual reflective journal is the application of the Belbin (1993) Team Roles Framework, undertaken online by each group member at the start of the project. Students are required to reflect on their Belbin outcome, through applying a reflective-writing framework in their journal, and to consider its perceived accuracy. They are also encouraged to reflect on all the other Belbin group-work personality types, so they gain a greater appreciation of others' working styles, both their strengths and weaknesses. Students have frequently commented on how valuable they find this Belbin analysis, not only in terms of gaining a better understanding of their own group-working strengths and weaknesses, but also in giving them a greater appreciation of how to better manage their project groups, through a better understanding of others' group-work roles. The need for lecturer intervention in group-project disputes has reduced significantly, making it feasible to continue to run group projects in large classes (60 project groups in one semester). A proposal for further research to test the efficacy of the Belbin Framework, as a project group management tool in a large-class context, is discussed.

Keywords: *Belbin Framework; Group-work; Individual reflective journal; Self-directed learning; Large-classes*

1. Introduction

In the context of growing class sizes and reduced administrative / tutorial support, there can be a tendency to forgo, or remove, learning elements that might be considered administratively demanding, such as group projects. At the same time, there is significant research to suggest the value of group-work (see literature review below). The author has been actively researching different methods to support group-work of a high standard in large-class settings, while also ensuring that they do not require substantial lecturer / tutor support. In this he is very keen to identify how technology and self-directed learning can reduce the administrative burden, while at the same time maintaining a high standard of group-work. He has previously researched the effectiveness of a group project diary to reduce group conflict and the need for lecturer / tutor intervention (Murphy and Winkler, 2023). He now describes how an individual reflective journal (learning log), based on the Belbin Team Roles Framework, can be used to assist students to manage their group-work more effectively, by enhancing their understanding of their own and their teammates' behaviour in the course of undertaking group-work. References are made to the use of Canvas throughout this paper. For those unfamiliar with Canvas, it is the online teaching resource used by the author's university, having previously used Blackboard.

2. Description of the Teaching / Learning Context

The author is a lecturer who uses group-projects in two different 'large-class' modules, with a combined student registration of around 320 students (varying slightly each year due to elective student registrations). Both modules require students to undertake extensive applied research for their group projects, which are central to the module learning and assessment. In recent years module numbers have increased at the same time that tutor and other administrative support has decreased. Therefore the lecturer is having to oversee around 60 group projects in one semester. The lecturer had also seen an increase in the number of group-project issues arising, some years ago, requiring more of his time to manage group disputes, particularly around the 'free-rider' problem, Murphy and Winkler (2023). A group project diary, introduced some years ago has reduced many of these issues arising. He is also keen to understand how students can better manage their own group-work in a large-class setting through more self-directed learning. This learning also contributes to greater personal development and preparation for 'real-world' group work during placement and later on in the workforce. The project for both modules is undertaken in groups of five, pre-selected by the lecturer to achieve a balanced mix of students by gender and nationality. There is limited tutor support on both modules, greatly reduced from previous years. As post-graduate / PhD students increasingly secure funding which restricts the time they are permitted to spend providing teaching support, this has resulted in fewer resources for tutorial support.

2.1. Description of the Individual Reflective Journal

At the beginning of the semester students are given the template for the reflective journal on Canvas. They are required to make two submissions, via Canvas: the first a month after they begin their project; the second just after they complete their project. This has been reduced from more frequent journal entries in the two previous years of this journal being implemented. This is due to the added time involved in overseeing and grading contributions, and the limited value observed of having additional journal entries. All of this activity is now conducted online, with no paperwork or email submissions. Students are required to undertake the Belbin Framework analysis online and to then reflect on their Belbin result. They are also asked to reflect on other learning they have developed in the course of undertaking the group project, using a choice of selected reflective-writing frameworks, Gibbs (1988), Kolb (2014), Schon (1991), which are all provided on Canvas. The individual reflective journal represents 10% of the final module grade, enough marks to ensure students undertake it, but not so much that it will take up considerable time and effort, given the other elements required to be completed on the module.

The learning logs are graded on a 'fail / pass / honours' basis (0%, 40% and 100%, respectively), to allow students to be honest in their self-assessment, as they are only marked on whether they applied the requisite frameworks, met the word-count and demonstrated adequate reflection. Therefore students do not feel under pressure to give an 'acceptable' answer or reflection (this grading strategy has allowed students to admit to having done very little on the group project, to being 'too bossy' etc., but still get full marks for their journal entry). This also makes grading easier for the lecturer, given the reduction in assistant examiner support in recent years. Almost all students get the top grade. This can also be motivating for their wider module engagement. Only about 1% of the students fail to submit the journal at all.

2.2. Description of how the Belbin Framework is Applied

Traditionally, the Belbin Framework is used as a tool to create more 'balanced' teams, in terms of getting the best mix of group-work personality types in each team (often with mixed results, see the literature review below). However, it is used here as an awareness-raising and personal-learning tool, to assist students reflect on their working styles and behaviour while engaged in team-work, and also to give them greater awareness of the other group-work personalities that exist. Students are advised, at the beginning of the semester, both in-class and online, that the main purpose of this exercise is to increase awareness, and that they do not have to subscribe to the accuracy of this personality test. Indeed, over the years, some students have stated they do not agree with the Belbin test's overall premise or accuracy, but it did make them think about their own, and others', behaviour when working in groups. This is the objective of this exercise. However, the majority of students who commented, have stated that they have found their Belbin result to be very accurate for the most part, and even

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more so by the end of the project, when they reflected on it again. A proposal for more detailed research to investigate this observation is presented below.

2.3. Focus on Self-directed Learning and Technology

Underlying the mechanism to run the reflective journal is the need to ensure it does not significantly contribute to the existing administrative work-load of the lecturer of a large-class, with many group projects. Apart from some explanation of the self-reflection process and the Belbin self-assessment, as part of the introductory lecture for the module, students are directed to Canvas where all the instruction is given. The Belbin self-assessment test is posted on Canvas. Results, as part of the first reflective journal entry, are also posted on Canvas. The lecturer can see, in one page on Canvas, if students have submitted their first journal entry, without having to open any of them. The various reflective-writing tools are given in the journal template on Canvas, along with a series of videos explaining the reflective-writing process and how to apply these tools. Again, this does not require lecturer input or lecture time, and constitutes part of the 'self-directed learning' element of the module. For this reason, it is ideal for a 'large-class teaching' scenario, as it effectively 'runs itself' along with also giving students important skills in managing their own learning through technology. Students are then required to re-submit their first journal entry, along with their final journal entry, into the reflective journal template, so the lecturer only has to review the final document. As the grade is on a 'fail / pass / honours' basis, above, and is based on whether the appropriate frameworks are applied, that the word-count is met and that there is adequate evidence of sufficient reflection, the grading is not onerous.

3. Literature Review

Group-work has been widely recommended as an effective means of experiential learning and professional development, Fearon et al. (2012), while employers are increasingly looking for learning methods that enhance student employability (Knight and Yorke, 2003). However, maintaining a satisfactory standard of experiential learning in a large-class setting can come with many challenges (Donovan and Hood, 2021). In spite of this there has been limited research into identifying mechanisms that mitigate the challenges of using experiential learning in large classes (Black *et al.*, 2021). According to Page *et al.* (2021), effective management of experiential learning does not mean that 'big' is always 'bad'. One mechanism being proposed here is to use the 'Belbin Framework', (Belbin, 1993), as a means to give students a greater awareness of both their own working styles in a group-setting, along with a deeper appreciation of the working styles of others. This is done with the intention that they can then better manage their own team work without seeking external (lecturer) intervention.

The standard application of the Belbin Framework is to try to ensure more 'balanced' work teams, at the team creation stage, by identifying the different team roles that various team

members might more effectively assume. The research on the effectiveness of the Belbin Framework is 'scant' and mixed, in terms of whether it leads to more effective teams, in a controlled experiment. Henry and Stevens (1999), found that team effectiveness increased where leadership roles, based on using the Belbin Framework, were intentionally assigned. Pritchard and Stanton (1999) state that there has not been enough empirical evidence to support the validity of the Belbin approach, in spite of it being used frequently by organisations and management consultancies. In a test they conducted they found that 'mixed teams', according to the Belbin Framework, performed better than randomly formed teams where roles were duplicated. However, in a controlled experiment, where some teams were created according to the Belbin Framework and others were not, amongst one cohort of students undertaking the same group-work, Batenburg *et al.* (2013) state that "*no relationship was found between team role diversity and team performance*" overall. Fisher *et al.* (1996) found the Belbin self-perception inventory data to be weaker than other frameworks in terms of reliability in a 'test-retest' study. However, the purpose of the current application of the Belbin Framework, is to create awareness of students of their own possible strengths and weaknesses when working in a team, and also of those of other team-working personality types. In that context it is not relevant whether the teams are mixed or not. However, when first applied to the module, some students assumed they had to perform a certain team role, based on their Belbin self-assessment, so it had to be explained clearly, in subsequent years, that the framework is being used here purely as an awareness-raising and self-reflective tool, and not to identify roles for students to perform as part of their team-work.

4. Suggestions for Further Research

While, a priori, based on student commentary over the last three years, the individual reflective journal has been well received by students, and the Belbin framework considered to be helpful, there is a significant opportunity to undertake more structured research using data from student journals and also surveys of students who engage in this process. The author is currently preparing to undertake such research. It is also intended to undertake research into the different learnings that students have gained from the self-reflection and from using the Belbin framework. By far, the most repeated comment by students to date is that they wish they had not been afraid to voice their opinions at the beginning of the project. In terms of the greater awareness of others' working styles, some of the most noticeable comments were from students who identified as having strong / confident personality types and, prior to undertaking the Belbin analysis, just assumed that those who do not speak up are lazy or uninterested. This suggests much scope for a detailed study into the benefits of the reflective process for students engaging in group work, often for the first time. Students have also commented that the Belbin self-assessment should be done at the programme level, before they first undertake any group projects, rather than being only module-specific in the later years of their studies.

The other key benefit of such research is to identify how the Belbin framework can be used as an awareness-raising tool, particularly for students not accustomed to working in groups, without the need to use it to balance team formation. However there is also scope to use the Belbin framework, as originally devised, to assist create the project teams. In this case students would undertake the Belbin self-assessment and post their result to the lecturer, who would then structure the project teams for the semester based on this information. A study could then be undertaken across the two modules, where this is done for one module but not for the other, to see if there is any significant difference in team performance and outcomes, and when also compared to previous years for both modules.

5. Analysis of / Reflection on / Implications for Practice

The Belbin Framework can be used to assist students enhance their awareness of both their own strengths and weaknesses while undertaking group work, while also enabling them to gain a better understanding of the working styles of other team members. When this is undertaken online, via a teaching platform like Canvas, it can be a part of 'self-directed' learning and it virtually eliminates the need for academic administrative support. It is presented here as one tool that can be easily administered within a large-class setting, to enhance the group-work experience and also to reduce the likelihood of the need for lecturer intervention in any group disputes. Since introducing various tools, such as the reflective journal and the group project diary, the author has experienced a very significant reduction in the number of project group disputes requiring his attention. Apart from these benefits, the opportunity to reflect on one's behaviour and thinking, while engaged in a challenging project, is an important part of students' deeper personal growth, and their development of valuable 'soft' skills.

The experience to date demonstrates that the Belbin framework analysis, as part of a wider self-reflection process, can be successfully conducted in large classes, online, without lecturer or tutor support, once it is set up carefully. The a priori evidence to date suggests students find this exercise very beneficial. Further research should be undertaken to confirm this and to also identify more effective ways to use such frameworks online in large classes as part of student self-directed learning.

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